

Synthesis of New 2-Oxazolinium Salts and their Betaine Structure

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Several new 2,3-dialkyl-2-oxazolinium salts have been prepared from the reaction of 2-alkyl-2-oxazolines with alkyl bromides. ¹H nmr studies reveal that these salts exist in solution in the form of a betaine structure.

In connection with the synthesis of annelated azaphospholes^{1,2}, we have prepared several new 2,3-dialkyl-2-oxazolinium bromides which undergo an interesting phenomenon of proton loss to form a betaine structure which has been observed for the first time.

bromide afforded 2,3-dialkyl-2-oxazolinium bromides (3) in quantitative yields (Scheme 1) (Table 1). The products are crystalline solids or syrupy mass soluble in common organic solvents. These salts were found to be highly hygroscopic and were stable only under nitrogen.

In the ¹H nmr spectra of these salts, the expected singlet for ³N-CH₂-protons at δ 4.0–5.5

Scheme 1

Results and Discussion

2-Alkyl-2-oxazoline on treating with an alkyl

TABLE I—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF 2,3-DIALKYL-2-OXAZOLINIUM BROMIDES (3)

Compd. no.	R	R ¹	M.p. °C	Yield %	δ ^a
					J (Hz)
3a	H	COC ₆ H ₅	158–60	42	2.99 (3H, s, 2-CH ₃), 3.88 (2H, t, ³ J _{HH} 6.0, H-4), 4.38 (2H, t, ³ J _{HH} 6.0, H-5), 7.50–7.90 (5H, m, C ₆ H ₅), 8.71 (s, N-CH)
b	H	C ₆ H ₅	140–42	38	2.19 (3H, s, 2-CH ₃), 4.29 (2H, t, ³ J _{HH} 6.0, H-4), 4.56 (2H, t, ³ J _{HH} 6.0, H-5), 7.37–7.82 (5H, m, C ₆ H ₅), 9.60 (bs, N-CH)
c	H	COOC ₂ H ₅	Semisolid	24	1.33 (3H, t, ³ J _{HH} 7.1, CH ₂ CH ₃), 2.17 (3H, s, 2-CH ₃), 3.48–3.58 (2H, unresolved m, H-4), 4.31 (2H, q, ³ J _{HH} 7.1, OCH ₂), 4.57 (2H, t, ³ J _{HH} 5.5, H-5), 9.42 (bs, N-CH)
d	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	122–24	26	1.15 (3H, t, ³ J _{HH} 7.0, CH ₃), 2.49 (2H, q, ³ J _{HH} 7.0, 2-CH ₂), 4.30 (2H, t, ³ J _{HH} 6.5, H-4), 4.49 (2H, t, ³ J _{HH} 6.5, H-5), 7.30–7.60 (5H, m, C ₆ H ₅), 9.60 (bs, N-CH)
e	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃ (p)	160–61	41	1.14 (3H, t, ³ J _{HH} 7.0, CH ₂ CH ₃), 2.41 (3H, s, CH ₃), 2.55 (2H, q, ³ J _{HH} 7.0, 2-CH ₂), 4.15 (2H, t, ³ J _{HH} 6.0, H-4), 4.56 (2H, t, ³ J _{HH} 6.0, H-5), 7.17–7.71 (4H, m, C ₆ H ₅), 9.58 (bs, N-CH)
f	CH ₃	COOCH ₃	120–21	37	1.16 (3H, t, ³ J _{HH} 7.5, CH ₃), 2.60 (2H, q, ³ J _{HH} 7.5, 2-CH ₂), 3.27–3.54 (2H, unresolved m, H-4), 3.74 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 4.48 (2H, t, ³ J _{HH} 6.0, H-5), 9.33 (bs, N-CH)
g	CH ₃	COOC ₂ H ₅	Syrupy	40	1.14 (3H, t, ³ J _{HH} 7.4, 2-CH ₂ CH ₃), 1.37 (3H, t, ³ J _{HH} 7.1, OCH ₂ CH ₃), 2.47 (2H, q, ³ J _{HH} 7.4, 2-CH ₂), 3.53 (2H, t, ³ J _{HH} 4.8, H-4), 4.30 (2H, q, ³ J _{HH} 7.1, OCH ₂), 4.58 (2H, t, ³ J _{HH} 5.0, H-5), 7.31 (bs, N-CH)

* 3a in DMSO-d₆ and 3b-g in CDCl₃

was found to be absent^{1,2}. Instead a broad singlet was observed unexpectedly in the downfield region at δ 7.31–9.60 which could be attributed to the methine proton on the anionic carbon of the *N*-cycloimmonium ylides³. A peak of varying sharpness at δ 2.48–4.82 probably results due to traces of water.

These results could be explained due to proton loss from the acidic *N*-methylene group to generate a betaine **4** (Scheme 2).

Scheme 2

The singlet at δ 7.31–9.60 was attributed to the proton present on the anionic carbon as observed in the ylidic species³. It had been reported⁴ that cyclic oxygen in 2-methyloxazoline caused a strong mesomeric effect which reduced deshielding of 2-methyl group. However, in 2,3-dialkyloxazolinium bromides the methylene/methyl protons (δ 2.17–3.30) of 2-alkyl groups were found to be more deshielded than the corresponding protons in the 2-alkyloxazoline (δ 2.01–2.32)⁴. This indicates that oxygen does not participate in mesomerism in these salts. The resulting betaine structure was stabilised due to electrostatic attraction as in *N*-pyridinium and other *N*-cycloimmonium ylides^{5,6}. It may be mentioned that this type of phenomenon was not observed¹ in 2,3-dialkyl-2-thiazolinium bromides. From these results it can be concluded that oxygen of the oxazoline ring enhances the electron-deficient character of the immonium nitrogen which makes the loss of proton from *N*-methylene group possible.

Experimental

2-Alkyloxazolines and substituted alkyl bromides (Aldrich) were used as such. Diethyl ether was dried over sodium wire and stored over molecular sieve (4A). Melting points were determined by capillary method on a Tempo apparatus and are uncorrected. ¹H nmr spectra (CDCl₃ or DMSO-d₆) were recorded on a Jeol FX 90Q instrument using TMS as internal standard.

2,3-Dialkyloxazolinium salts : To a solution of substituted alkyl bromide (0.05 mol) in diethyl ether (40 ml), 2-alkyloxazoline (0.05 mol) was added and the resulting reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature (25°) for 2–4 days. In case of **3a**, the resulting cream coloured solid was washed with diethyl ether (2 × 20 ml) and dried under reduced pressure. However, in case of **3b** and **3d–f**, a syrupy mass was obtained after removing the solvent under reduced pressure. The oily mass was macerated with diethyl ether repeatedly, whereupon it solidified. The salts **3c** and **3g**, however, did not solidify even under these conditions.

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References

1. R. K. BANSAL, R. MAHNOT, D. C. SHARMA, K. KARAGHISOFF and A. SCHMIDPETER, *Heteroatom Chem.*, 1992, **3**, 351.
2. R. K. BANSAL, R. MAHNOT, D. C. SHARMA and K. KARAGHISOFF, *Synthesis*, 1992, 267.
3. W. G. PHILLIPS and K. W. RATTS, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1970, **35**, 3144.
4. M. A. WEINBERGER and R. GREENHALGH, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1963, **41**, 1038.
5. A. W. JOHNSON, "Ylid Chemistry", Academic, New York, 1966.
6. I. ZUGRAVESCU and M. PETROVANU, "N-Ylid-Chemistry", McGraw-Hill, New York, 1976.